

First observation of *Raphidiopsis* (*Cylindrospermopsis*) *raciborskii* (Nostocales) during a heatwave in Lake Comabbio (Northern Italy)

Fig. 1. Collection site showing the location of the *Raphidiopsis* (*Cylindrospermopsis*) *raciborskii* bloom.

We report the first documented observation of the freshwater filamentous cyanobacteria *Raphidiopsis raciborskii* (synonyms *Anabaena raciborskii*, *Cylindrospermopsis raciborskii*) in Northern Italy, specifically in Lake Comabbio during July 2015. Previously, *C. raciborskii* blooms were observed in Central Italy and Sardinia. This species is considered an invasive and potentially toxic filamentous cyanobacterium, originally described as a tropical species, now spreading into temperate regions. It can produce toxins like cylindrospermopsin and saxitoxins, which pose a significant health risk to animals and humans. These toxins have been demonstrated to bioaccumulate in aquatic invertebrates, and they can lead to mass mortalities of fish and birds. The increasing intensity and duration of heatwaves, predicted to rise this century, create favorable conditions for harmful, bloom-forming freshwater cyanobacteria, necessitating heightened monitoring of these evolving risks.

In recent years, *R. raciborskii* has expanded globally, particularly in temperate regions [1], due to its tolerance to a wide range of climatic conditions. This bloom-forming species, typically found in eutrophic waters, usually does not generate surface scums but shows a relatively uniform distribution throughout the euphotic zone [2, 3]. Factors such as global, eutrophication, and hydrological changes [4–6] are driving the expansion

of cyanobacteria, often occurring simultaneously [7]. In Italy, blooms of *R. raciborskii* were first observed in Central Italy in 1995 at Trasimeno Lake, followed by Albano Lake in 2002 and Cedrino Lake in Sardinia in 2003. A further study in 2004 revealed the presence of cylindrospermopsin in two of these lakes [8].

In July 2015, during a heat wave, a bloom dominated by *R. raciborskii* occurred in Lake Comabbio, a small, eutrophic, shallow polymictic lake in Northwest Italy, which is also a Natura 2000 Site and a Special Area of Conservation (ZSC IT2010008) (Fig. 1). The lake has a large watershed relative to its surface area. The inflow is provided by rainfall, groundwater and small tributaries which consist exclusively of minor torrential watercourses except for a small stream [10] and its naturally high trophic level is exacerbated by slow hydrological renewal and nutrient loading from domestic effluents [11].

Phytoplankton composition and

abundance were assessed using samples preserved in acetic Lugol's solution, and the abundance was quantified according to Uthermöhl method using an inverted microscope Leica DMI4000b at 20x, 40x and 100x magnification. Saxitoxin concentrations were quantified using enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA). The analysis was conducted on frozen samples. Saxitoxin total content (intracellular plus dissolved toxin) was measured on the whole water samples, after freeze-thawing twice. For immunochemical detection (ELISA), 5 mL water samples were filtered by membrane filters (0.22 mm, Millex-GV), and analyzed directly with a commercially available ABRAXIS® Saxitoxin (PSP) ELISA Microtiter Plate (Abraxis, Los Angeles, California, USA), by measuring the absorbance at 450 nm (Wallac Victor2 spectrofluorometer, Perkin Elmer Inc, USA). The detection limit was 0.015 ng/ml. No cylindrospermopsin analysis were performed because this toxin standard was not available.

Chl-a concentration maps were derived from satellite data by applying a bio-optical model previously corrected for atmospheric effects. Chl-a products were obtained from images of the MSI sensor on board of the European Space Agency's SENTINEL-2 satellite with a

Fig. 2. *Raphidiopsis* (*Cylindrospermopsis*) *raciborskii*: trichome collected from Lake Comabbio (100x).

Fig. 3. Chl-a derived from Sentinel-2A imagery in Lake Comabbio.

spatial resolution of 10 meters, while for surface water temperature two products were obtained from the TIRS sensor aboard NASA's LANDSAT-8 satellite. For meteorological data, a dataset for the year 2015 based on daily average temperature (in °C) was provided by Centro Geofisico Prealpino <https://www.astrogeo.va.it/meteo/>

R. raciborskii in Lake Comabbio was primarily observed as straight fila-

Fig. 4. Surface temperature maps derived from Landsat-8 imagery in Lake Comabbio.

ments with terminal drop-shaped heterocytes with pointed ends (Fig. 2). Coiled trichomes and akinetes were not observed, and heterocytes were observed generally at one end of the trichome. The average density of *R. raciborskii* on July 24th was 2.5×10^9 cells·L⁻¹, representing almost the total phytoplankton community. The highest density was 2.6×10^{10} cells·L⁻¹, while the lowest was 1.9×10^8 cells·L⁻¹.

Chemical analysis of lake samples revealed saxitoxin concentrations of 0,27 to 0,36 µg·L⁻¹, investigated through ELISA immunoassay analysis, and were correlated with *R. raciborskii* presence.

For chlorophyll estimation, satellite images were atmospherically corrected with the 6S radiative transfer code and the obtained reflectances were converted into Chl-a concentrations by means of a semi-empirical algorithm based on the ratios between the reflectances in the regions between 700 and 650 nm. Satellite-derived Chl-a concentrations ranged from 30 mg·m⁻³ to 40 mg·m⁻³ in the littoral zones (Fig. 3). Two satellite-derived temperature maps were available for the study period (20th July and 6th August), and we focused on the image from 20th July. Superficial temperatures showed a mean value of 30.8°C with a maximum of 34.2°C (Fig. 4). The heat wave in July 2015 was the longest on record, surpassing previous records of 2003 and 2014. Maximum temperatures exceeded 30°C for 26 consecutive days, from June 30th to July 25th.

Saxitoxins were detected at low concentrations, but further analysis via high-performance liquid chromatography (HPLC) is necessary. Landsat-8 and Sentinel-2A satellite data were instrumental in confirming the high Chl-a concentrations associated with this bloom, which occurred alongside high surface temperatures. Satellite and mi-

croscopic data were consistent, reinforcing the challenge in detecting this type of bloom, which does not form visible surface scums and only slightly alters water color. Due to the presence of cyanotoxins, this emerging threat to public health underscores the need for effective monitoring systems. Additionally, raising public awareness and informing stakeholders about the risks associated with these toxins is critical for ensuring community safety and well-being.

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